

A Study on Customers Attitude towards Advertising Media with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

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Abstract

Advertising is a measure of the growth of civilization and an indication of the striving of the human race for betterment and perfection. An assessment of the role of advertising in the economic system includes its role as a guide to prospective buyers for innovative products and services, for creating autonomous and derived demand among consumers, for facilitating them to make product differentiation and in the creation of higher propensity to consume such items besides providing financial support to the media. Media effects of advertising are visible from its influence on the efficiency of production and distribution, lowering of prices, economic well-being, improvements in the product quality and finally in its contribution to the national income. It also helps people and organizations to find each other and create or sustain thousands of jobs, both in advertising agencies and in various promotion and exhibition industries.

Keywords: Advertising; Media effects; Consumer Attitude.

Introduction

Advertising is closely linked with economic development, as it is a vital marketing input, especially at the stage of introduction of a new product. It is an instrument of persuasion and information and the informative role of advertisements consist of providing information about products, their specifications, features, functions and prices to prospective buyers. It is an invaluable aid in the process of market development. Advertising also performs the useful functions like the dissemination of information about innovative technologies, creation of favourable conditions conducive to the consumers in satiating their demands and in making them to accept innovative products and services hitherto unknown to them. Economic systems are basically constituted by a series of transactions between individuals, organizations and sectors. Advertisements released by the Loss Prevention Association of India, urging people to prevent losses, avoid accidents and advertisements released by the cancer society of India Moreover and several other advertisements of a similar nature does play important roles in the society. Companies and institutions resort to various types of advertisements for effectively communicating with the public at large about the community services rendered by them.

Customer Attitude and Sellers: Towards Advertising

Advertising through visual symbols are extensively used at present by many of the firms and advertising agencies as an effective medium to communicate the matter to the prospective consumers at a much faster rate than word descriptions because they involve less mental effort to them than thinking in terms of words. Sellers depend on advertising for launching of their new products services, while buyers come to know about the different attributes of such products I services, the sources from which they are available, prominent brands, etc.

Statement of the Problem

Media Efficiency is a primary goal of advertisement. An Increasing competitive marketing environment, unprecedented audience fragmentation and steadily increasing number of media and promotional options have continued to create uncertainty for late advertisement and media executives. Today the markets are flooded with different types of

advertisement. Each advertisement is trying to attract the customer by introducing innovations. This has forced the research to find out to what extent advertisements create an impact and influence on the purchase decision of the customer.

Objectives of the Study

1. To Study the level of awareness about different media among the Respondents.
2. To ascertain the type of media preferred by the respondents.
3. To Study the impact of advertisements on the respondents level.
4. To Determine the influence of media on the purchasing Decision of the Respondents.

Research Methodology

A Research design is the arrangement of collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure.

(i) Data

The study is based on primary data. It has been collected through a questionnaire from various respondents during the period from April 2014 to September 2014. Secondary data from the books, Journals and websites have been collected and used wherever necessary.

(ii) Sampling

Data has been collected from 250 respondents of Coimbatore city by the convenient sampling method.

Tools for Analysis

Data collected through the questionnaire has been rearranged and entered in a master table. It is reclassified and entered in a number of tables as per the needs of the study. Statistical tools such as,

- (i) Simple Percentage Analysis
- (ii) Chi-square
- (iii) ANOVA
- (iv) Weighted average method
- (v) Garrett ranking scale and Rank order method.

Review of Literature

Jerome D. Scott's (1988) opinion the effects on advertising outlays upon profit and liquidity are important considerations in setting outer limits for advertising. He also describes that normally a time lag occurs between advertising outlay and sale results. In his opinion the firm's resources set a real limit on advertising outlay.

Winter (1988) Studied on "A laboratory experiment of Individual attitude in response to advertising exposures "with an objective of examining the influence or advertising change. The conclusion derived from the study suggested that the more familiar a consumer is with a brand, the less are the chances of any possible attitude change and that only prior negative attitude may turn positive as a result of advertising exposures.

In C.V. Marnorla et al (1992) opinion an effective advertisement should be done strictly in the language of the customer and it should be inserted at the right time in the right place and also in the right media. Moreover the advertisement should be communicated to the people on whom it is aimed.

Nabi M.K et al (1994) conducted a survey on "Television as a media of advertising."The objective of the study is to examine the influence of television buyers. It was found that 44% of the respondents expressed television is the best and followed by newspaper(26%).They concluded that television as a medium of advertising is the best thing that has happened to market and has surpassed other media in terms of reach.

Samudhrarakumar.C et al (1997) has studied on "consumers attitude towards advertisements "with an aim to measure both the positive and negative aspects of advertisements. He concluded that the advertisement creators must concentrate more on the information and social aspects in any advertising and must avoid advertising for harmful products and exploitation of women. They suggested that the government must also play a key role in framing regulations regarding advertisement relating to exploitation of women.

Analysis and Interpretation

Advertising plays a significant role in today's highly competitive world. Today new areas are emerging with advertising like event management, image management, internet marketing etc, Successful use of data depends for a large extended upon manner in which it is arranged, dispatched and summarized. Data was collected from various respondents through questionnaire and work sheet was prepared from which analysis and interpretations were arranged.

Demographic factors:

Particulars	Factors	Number of respondents	Percentage
Age years	Less than 25	110	44
	26-35 years	79	31.6
	36-45 years	44	17.3
	Above 45 years	18	7.2
Gender	Male	106	42.4
	Female	144	57.6
Marital status	Married	122	48.8
	Unmarried	128	51.2
Educational Qualification	Up to school level	53	21.2
	Undergraduate	108	43.2
	Postgraduate	51	20.4
	Professional	30	12
	Others	8	3

Media Awareness:

Media	Highly aware	%	Aware	%	Neutral	%	Not aware	%	Total
Print	128	51.2	117	46.8	3	1.2	2	0.4	250
Telecast	140	56	98	39.2	11	4.4	1	0.4	250
Outdoor	59	23.6	133	53.2	53	21.2	5	2	250
Direct mail	35	14	98	39.2	92	36.8	25	10	250
Online	36	14.4	55	22	103	41.2	56	22.4	250

Regarding Outdoor media majority 53.2% of the respondents are aware, the remaining 23.6% of the respondents are highly aware, The table shows that majority 51.2% of the respondents are highly aware about the print media. Regarding broadcast media 56% of the respondents have highly aware while 39.2% have aware. In Outdoor media majority 53.2% of the respondents In direct mail advertisement 39.2% of the respondents are aware, next to 36.8% of the respondents are neutral about the direct mail advertisement.

Effective place in Print Media Advertisement

Particulars	Strongly Agree	%	Agree	%	Neutral	%	Disagree	%	Strongly disagree	%
First page	72	28.8	93	37.2	74	29.6	8	3.2	3	1.2
Last page	45	18	107	42.8	78	31.3	15	6	5	2
Other page	20	8	55	22	115	46	46	18.4	14	5.6

The table shows that, In first page most 37.2% of the respondents agree about the effectiveness. Regarding last page, Majority 42.8% of the respondents feel agree, next 45% of the respondents are feel that the effectiveness of last page is strongly agree. At the last the other pages of the advertisement is most 46% of the respondents tells that the effectiveness is neutral.

Factors Influencing the Television Advertisement

The respondents are classified on the basis of factors influencing in television advertisement

Factors	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Music	59	23.6
Dramatic sketches	32	12.8
Events of the society	39	15.6
Short play	31	12.4
Skits	26	10.4
Fashion	27	11.6
Product demonstration	29	11.6
News	5	2
Sports	2	0.8
Total	250	100

The table 4.5.1 shows that most 23.6% of the respondents are influencing by music, next 15.6% of the respondents are influenced by events of the society, whereas 12.8% of the respondents are influence by dramatic sketches, in case of short play only 12.4% of the respondents are influenced, next 11.6% of the respondents influenced by product demonstration, where as 10.8% of the respondents are influence by fashion. Next 10.4% of the respondents are influenced by skits.

Factors Influencing Outdoor Advertisement

Factors	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Caption	40	16
Pasteurisation	86	34.4
Message	89	35.6
Whole copy of the advertisement	35	14
Total	250	100

The table 4.6.2 shows that most 35.6% of the respondents influence by message, another 34.4% of the respondents getting influence by picturisation, next 16% of the respondents feels caption is the influencing factor, remaining 14% of the respondents influence by whole copy of the advertisement.

Preference towards Direct Mail Advertisement

Type of Advertisement	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Circulars	18	7.2
Business reply envelop cards	36	14.4
Price lists	37	14.8
Catalogues	60	24
Leaflets folders	30	12
Booklets	28	11.2
Gift novelties	23	9.2
Personal letters	14	5.6
Others	4	1.6
Total	250	100

The table shows that 24% of the respondents prefer catalogues in outdoor advertisement, next 14.8% of the respondents prefer pricelists, another 14.4% of their respondents prefer business reply envelop cards, 12% of the respondents prefer leaflets & folders, 11.2% of the respondents prefer booklets, another 9.2% of the respondents prefer gift novelties, 7.2% of the respondents prefer circulars, only 5.6% of the respondents prefer personal letters at last 1.6% of the respondents prefer other type of direct mail advertisement.

Preference and Impact of online Advertisement

Forms of online advertisement	Number of respondents	Percentage
Website	78	31.2
Banners	64	25.6
Buttons	29	11.6
Sponsorship	39	15.6
Classified adds	40	16
Total	250	100

The table reveals that 31.2% of the respondents impact by websites. Next 25.6% of the respondents impact by banners. Another 11.6% of the respondents impact by buttons, next 15.6% of the respondents impact by sponsorship, another 16% of the respondents impact by classified adds.

Chi-Square Test:-

Relationship between Monthly Income and Impact of Online Advertisement

Hypothesis:

H_0 : Let us take the hypothesis that there is no relationship between Monthly income and Impact of online advertisement.

TABLE 4.10.6

Monthly Income	Forms of online Advertisement					Total
	Website	Banners	Buttons	Sponsorship	Classified adds	
Up to 10000	7	4	2	1	2	16
10001-20000	18	10	7	9	7	51
20001-30000	16	32	12	18	18	96
30001-40000	18	13	5	6	10	52
Above40000	19	5	3	5	3	35
Total	78	64	29	39	40	250

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (r-1)(c-1) \\ &= (5-1)(5-1) = (4)(4) = 16 \end{aligned}$$

Calculated chi-square value at 5% level of significance = 23.71

Table value at 5% level of significance = 26.3

The calculated chi-square value is less than the table value of 5% level of significance. So that the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it is concluded that there is no associate relationship between Income and Impact of online Advertisement.

Enova Test:-

4.11.6 Relationship between Educational Qualification and Impact of Online Advertisement

To ascertain the relationship between Educational Qualification and impact of online advertisement. The following hypothesis is framed:

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and impact of online advertisement.

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F Ratio	5%limit (from F table f(4,20))
between samples	299.6	(5-1)=4	74.9	1.022	2.8661
within samples	1465.6	(25-5)=20	73.28		
Total	1765.2	24			

The table value of F for $v_1=4, v_2=20$ at 5% level of significance is 2.8661. The calculated value of F is less than the table value of 5% level of significance. So the hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that, there is no significant relationship between Educational Qualification and Impact of online Advertisement.

Findings

- ❖ Majority 44% of the respondents are under the age group of less than 25 years.
- ❖ Majority 57.6% of the respondents are female.
- ❖ Majority 51.2% of the respondents are married.
- ❖ Most of 43.2% of the respondents are undergraduate.
- ❖ Majority 50% of the respondents are employed
- ❖ Majority 56% of the respondents are highly aware about the telecast media advertisement.
- ❖ Regarding outdoor media, majority 53.2% of the respondents are aware about the media advertisement.

- ❖ Majority 54.4% of the respondents are agree that they have repetitive effects in purchasing decision by telecast media.
- ❖ Most of 44.8% of the respondents are agree that the information is useful for them.
- ❖ Most 38.4% of the respondents feel neutral about the motivation to buy with the telecast media advertisement.
- ❖ 11.2% of the respondents are gave first rank to direct approach in direct mail advertisement.
- ❖ 38.4% of the respondents are affected by the cost of broadcast media advertisement. They feel agree about the cost.
- ❖ Most 46.4% of the respondents are impact the outdoor advertisement by simple and effective message.
- ❖ 35.6% of the respondents are influence by message of outdoor media advertisement.
- ❖ Most 40.4% of the respondents feel agree about the impact of direct mail advertisement in detail description about the product.
- ❖ Majority 52% of the respondents feel agree about the impact of direct mail advertisement in create personal contact.
- ❖ Most 39.6% of the respondents feel good about the wide range in online advertisement.
- ❖ Most 47.2% of the respondents feel good about the Elimination of middlemen in online advertisement.
- ❖ 37.2% of the respondents feel good about improves profit in online advertisement.

Suggestions

- ❖ Advertising should be simple and easy to understand.
- ❖ Advertisement should create awareness and acceptance of the brand preference.
- ❖ Advertisement should be more creative and enthusiastic.
- ❖ Advertisement should educate the consumers for right decision.
- ❖ Some of the respondents are low aware about the advertisements. Hence it is suggested that advertisers should create more awareness about advertising. So advertisers should concentrate on better selection of product.
- ❖ The overall view and suggestions of the respondents is, Advertising Medias are not only commercial bodies, but also they are intermediate of producer to buyer. They are concentrate not only to sales and earn profit, but also to maintaining healthy society.

Conclusion

Advertising plays an important role in the marketing field. Many products are aware through advertisement media only. So, Innovative advertisement should be developed as per the new technology, The public can be benefited if the advertisements are properly developed through different media. The more knowledge can provide the better productivity. Exchange media is an advertisement agency that has the knowledge as well as experience that will be a big benefit in making advertisement campaigns run successfully. Advertising media is actually brand-building through effective communication and is essentially a service industry. It helps to create demand, promote marketing system and boost economic growth. So that the overall advertising media serves as a transformer and an information support system to disseminate, filter and collect feedback or response about all events thus spreading awareness and making things happen.

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